

Are Triassic rocks of the Upper Rhine Graben a geothermal reservoir? Insights from Rittershoffen wells with geophysical logs and SWIR spectroscopy.

Carole Glaas¹, Manaarii Salmon², Fabien Baron², Guilherme Bozetti³, Gabriela Knobelock³, Gabrielle Rumbach¹, Patricia Patrier², Cécile Baczkowski^{1,4}, Albert Genter¹

¹ ES-Géothermie, 26 boulevard du Président Wilson, 67000 Strasbourg, France

² University of Poitiers, CNRS UMR 7285 IC2MP, HydrASA, Bat B8 rue Albert Turpain, TSA51106, F-86073 Poitiers Cedex 9, France

³ University of Strasbourg, CNRS ITES UMR 7063, 5, rue René Descartes, 67084 Strasbourg, France

⁴ ENSG, 2 rue du Doyen Roubault, 54505 Vandoeuvre lès Nancy, France

carole.glaas@es.fr

Keywords: Upper Rhine Graben, Short-Wave InfraRed spectroscopy, Muschelkalk, Buntsandstein, Triassic, geothermal reservoir, porosity, temperature, natural fractures, clay minerals

ABSTRACT

Over the past 20 years, deep geothermal wells exploited fractured reservoirs of granite and sandstone in the Upper Rhine Graben (URG). Nowadays, the porosity of the Triassic sandstones and limestones is also explored for potential geothermal and lithium resources. Therefore, the characterization of permeability/porosity of this matrix and fractured dual medium is essential. The reservoir quality of these continental to marine formations is hard to predict. We try to understand how hydrothermal circulations are controlled by structures of porosity (matrix versus fractures). The results allow identifying correlations between measurements on cuttings, static and dynamic well logs. These correlations are representative of the different types of media (fractures and matrix permeability).

1. INTRODUCTION

Since 2016, the geothermal doublet of Rittershoffen located in the French part of Upper Rhine Graben, has been exploiting the geothermal brine circulating in the porous and fractured Buntsandstein sandstone as well as in the fractured granite. But the fluid contribution of both formations is hard to discriminate. Since 1987, the fractured crystalline reservoir has been intensely investigated in the URG (Baujard et al., 2017; Evans et al., 2005). Therefore, we try to characterize the traces of fluid circulation in the Lower and Middle Triassic formations (Muschelkalk and Buntsandstein) based on mineralogical studies and various well logs.

In the fractured granite of the URG, the Short-Wave InfraRed (SWIR) spectroscopy coupled with X-Ray

Diffraction (XRD) already proved its efficiency by quantifying the clay minerals (illite, smectite) resulting from the hydrothermal alteration due to fluid circulation in the fractures (Glaas et al., 2019).

In order to generate unprecedented knowledge on clay mineralogy in the Lower and Middle Triassic formations in the URG, the SWIR spectroscopy is applied on 400 rock samples in these formations from the geothermal wells of Rittershoffen (Figure 1). This innovative exploration method is compared with standard static geophysical well logs and dynamic well logs.

The main objective of this study is to identify correlations between measurements on cuttings (calcimetry, SWIR spectroscopy), static geophysical logs (porosity, density, gamma ray), dynamic logs (temperature, gas venue, mud losses) and fracturation from image logs. These correlations are representative of the different types of media:

- Fractures and matrix permeability,
- Formation mineralogy (clay minerals and carbonates).

Hence, we will try to address the question: what supports fluid circulation more effectively, fractured and/or matrix reservoirs?

2. GEOLOGICAL AND GEOTHERMAL SETTING

The deep geothermal field of Rittershoffen is located on the western margin of the NE-SW-striking central segment of the URG (Figure 1). Over the granitic basement, sedimentary successions consist in Permian Lower Buntsandstein Group filling the remnant Variscan topography, overlain by continental sediments of the Lower Triassic Middle and Upper Buntsandstein groups and by the transgressive Middle Triassic Muschelkalk marine sequence, under a marine-

confined, evaporitic-dominated Upper Triassic. Above, a large Jurassic carbonate-dominated sequence is characterized by a total absence of Cretaceous. At this interface, a regional unconformity is observed and allow -in this part of the URG- Tertiary formations to cover Jurassic formations. Tertiary formations correspond to an Eocene-to recent sequence associated to the Eocene-Oligocene rifting system.

All this sedimentary sequence from the Quaternary to the Permian and even the Carboniferous basement are affected by numerous normal faults and their associated small-scale fractures system.

Favourable geothermal gradients (Pribnow and Schellschmidt, 2000), higher than 60°C/km, could be encountered at relatively shallow depths, and strong high-temperature anomalies also exist in this area (Baillieux et al., 2013). Typically, from the surface to the top of the Middle Triassic (Muschelkalk), a conductive zone is observed, which is located above a multi-kilometric vertical convective zone into which the geothermal fluid circulates. The natural permeability in the convective zone is shown to be governed by the natural fracture system embedded in an approximately impermeable matrix (Genter et al., 2010).

Consequently, natural faults play a major role in geothermal reservoir circulation and are the primary targets for geothermal exploitation. Therefore, almost all projects in the URG exploit the deep, fractured reservoirs located within the Permo-Triassic sediments and/or the crystalline basement (Soulitz-sous-Forêts, Bruchsal, Landau, Insheim, Rittershoffen).

The Rittershoffen project took advantages of the Soulitz-sous-Forêts experience, and the geothermal target was the Rittershoffen normal fault which is located approximately 15 km east of the western Rhenish border fault and is oriented N5°W based on subsurface geological data (Figure 1). The Rittershoffen fault intersects the Triassic sandstones, and the top of the fractured granitic basement at about 2500 m depth (Figure 1) (Baujard et al., 2017).

2.1 GRT-1 well

The first well, GRT-1, was drilled in 2012 to 2580 m MD, is nearly vertical and is used as injection well. The first testing results after drilling showed a low productivity Index ($PI < 0.5$ L/s/bar). A stimulation program, including thermal, chemical, and hydraulic stimulation, was therefore designed and successfully completed in 2013, increasing the hydraulic yield up to 2.5 L/s/bar (Baujard et al., 2017). Based on various borehole datasets, three major permeable zones linked to natural fracture occurrences were identified: two in the Muschelkalk, and one in the granite (Vidal et al., 2017). As the well has been cemented and tubed until 1922 m MD, only the permeable zone in the granite is present in the open-hole section and thus today exploited.

Figure 1: Geological map and cross-section of the Rittershoffen geothermal site showing well trajectories. Natural fracture orientations in Muschelkalk, Buntsandstein and granite are outlined.

2.2 GRT-2 well

GRT-2 well was drilled in 2014 and was slightly deviated but tangent to the local fault over its length of approximately 400 m of open-hole in the granitic basement (Figure 1). Its high productivity index of 4 L/s/bar without any stimulation revealed a good connection between the well and the fracture network (Baujard et al., 2017). The well probably intersects the fault zone characterized by a high fracture density with optimized natural fluid pathways (Vidal et al., 2017). The well is used as production well and 7 major permeable zones linked to fracture occurrences were identified: one in the Muschelkalk, two in the Buntsandstein and 4 in the granite (Vidal et al., 2017). As the well has been cemented and tubed until 2122 m MD, only the permeable zones in the Buntsandstein and in the granite are located in the open-hole section of the well and today exploited.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Cuttings

The cuttings (chip samples) collected during the drilling of the wells were first washed using sieves and then dried on-site in an oven at 80°C for 40 minutes, by the mud logger unit. In the case of the Triassic sections of the GRT-1 and GRT-2 wells, the cuttings were

sampled every 3 m in depth and depending on the well section considered, they represent varying rock volumes as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: representative volume of the cuttings, according to their sampling intervals and well sections

Well	Depth (m MD)	Lithology Interval (m TVD) Thickness (m)	Well diameter (in)	Sampling interval (m)	Number of samples	Volume (m ³)
GRT-1	1661-1808	Muschelkalk 1653 – 1798 145	12"1/4	3	47	0.15
	1808-1922	Buntsandstein 1798-2198 400	12"1/4	3	38	0.15
	1922-2212		8"1/2	3	87	0.07
GRT-2	1825-2022.5	Muschelkalk 1637-1793.5 156.5	12"1/4	3	66	0.15
	2022.5-2123	Buntsandstein 1793.5-2156 362.5	12"1/4	3	34	0.15
	2123-2479.5		8"1/2	3	117	0.07

3.2 Measurements on cuttings

The use of a calcimeter on the crushed and dried cuttings measures the quantity of CO₂ released by the reaction of the carbonates with HCl. The quantity of CO₂ released after 1 min gives the percentage of calcite, and the quantity of CO₂ released after 15 min gives the percentage of total carbonates. The difference between the total carbonates quantity and the calcite quantity is the amount of dolomite.

The SWIR spectra were acquired using a ASD TerraSpec® 4 Standard-Res field spectrometer associated with the Indico® Pro software. The spectrometer was composed to a fixed diffraction grating silicon (Si) array and two oscillating diffraction grating monochromators with indium gallium arsenide (InGaAs) detectors for the 350-1000 nm and the 1000-2500 nm spectral region, respectively. The spectral resolution is 3 nm in the 350-1000 nm range and 10 nm in the 1000-2500 nm range. A contact probe containing the white light source was used to analyse the samples. The calibration of detectors was done using a Spectralon® reflectance standard. Each sample spectrum corresponds to the average of 50 stacked spectra. The spectral total area parameter (arbitrary unit) was calculated on removed continuum spectra over the 1300-2500 nm range. The absorption bands in the 1850-2500 nm spectral range are characteristics of OH-bearing and CO₃²⁻ vibrations, indicative of hydroxylated and hydrated minerals such as phyllosilicates or carbonates. For a given mineral, the area of this characteristic band is proportional to their amount providing a semi-quantitative estimation of the mineral content along a borehole.

3.2 Static geophysical logs

As the hydrogen is present in water, an estimation of its amount in the porous formations will allow the estimation of the amount of liquid-filled porosity, the hydrogen index computed from neutron porosity log (NPHI) being directly associated to porosity (Serra and Serra, 2000). Porosity logs do not provide information on permeability but nevertheless provide a global signal

for fractured zones to the extent that they are porous and contain clays and fluids.

The density log is calculated from nuclear measurements emitted from a chemical source (Ce₁₃₇ and Co₆₀). A negative peak in a density curve could be due to clays and thus reveal alteration associated with a fracture zone, whereas positive peaks are associated with high-density minerals (like barite) or a change in lithology.

The gamma ray (GR) log measures natural radioactivity (uranium, potassium, and thorium), and aids in interpretations of lithology and rock composition. The potassium content is directly linked to the clay minerals occurrence.

Electrical resistivity was measured with five electrode configurations, yielding five apparent resistivity values (RLA1–5) (Schlumberger, 2018). These configurations are sensitive to different distances beyond the borehole wall. The shallowest resistivity (RLA1) reflects the average resistivity mainly of the borehole mud, and the deepest resistivity (RLA5) reflects the average resistivity of the formation. Electrical resistivity decreases in formations containing water and is even lower for conductive fluids that contain salts, such as brines. Similarly, electrical resistivity is low for clay minerals, pyrite, and hematite, which are conductive minerals. Resistivity logs are only available in GRT-2.

Ultrasonic Borehole Images (UBI) were acquired in both wells. A structural analysis of the macro fractures intersecting the well has been done based on borehole image log interpretation (Vidal et al., 2017).

Table 2: sampling resolution of the well logs used in this study

Data	Name	Unit	Vertical sampling <i>Horizontal sampling</i>
Static geophysical logs	NPHI Neutron porosity	m ³ /m ³	15 cm Depth of investigation: several cm (flushed zone)
	RHOZ density	g/cm	15 cm
	GR Gamma ray	gAPI	15 cm
	UBI Ultrasonic Borehole Images		1 cm 2°
	HRLA Electrical resistivity	ohm.m	15 cm Depth of investigation depending on the electrodes spacing
Dynamic well logs	temperature	°C	GRT-1 : 20 cm GRT-2 : 50 cm
	gas	ppm	Recorded in time and converted in depth each 50 cm
	mud	m ³ /h	

2.3 Dynamic logs

Temperature anomalies are reliable for the detection of fluid exchanges between the well and the formation (Vidal et al., 2019). The log should be acquired after the return of the well to the thermal equilibrium and the measurements are done downwards (Baujard et al., 2017). To better apprehend the temperature variations, the thermal gradient has also been represented (Figure 2) in order to identify small temperature variations.

Gas venues and mud losses are recorded by the driller during time and then the data is converted in depth. Gas venues allow to identify permeable zones as it is gas occurrences coming from the formation. Mainly methane (C1) has been reported. They can either come from permeable fracture zones or porous and permeable sections. Mud losses provide information on the quantity of mud that is lost through a permeable fractured zone in the well, and they are recorded by the driller and are thus approximations of the fracture zone permeability.

4. RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 GRT-1 well

A first description at a large scale is proposed, before detailing each permeable fracture zone and their well logs responses. All the depths are expressed in measured depth (MD).

The spatial distribution of the fractures in the Muschelkalk and the Buntsandstein of the GRT-1 well is organized in four main zones with varying fracture densities increasing with depth, correlated with SWIR responses (Figure 2).

The first upper zone is in the Muschelkalk from CC to the transition MB-CO or 1661 to 1755 m, with a density of 0.44 fractures per meter. Gas content is very stable in this section. This zone presents spectral total area duplicating the different trends of carbonate content curve and is marked by one important positive temperature anomaly and high positive peaks of total GR and K at the top of CC. The transition MB-CO presents high spectral total area, very high total GR and thermal gradient with a decrease of carbonate content and density. The high spectral total area coupled with the low carbonate content indicates a relatively high clay minerals content at the MB-CO transition. This trend shows a variation of thermal gradient surely due to the network of fractures.

The second zone begins at the interface between the Muschelkalk and the Buntsandstein from 1785 to 1907 m with a fracture density of 0.21 fractures per meter. In this low fracture density zone, the spectral total area evolves continuously reflecting a gradual evolution of the carbonate and clay minerals content. This spectral trend suggests that this zone is less influenced by the mineralogy linked to fractures but more by minerals with a sedimentary origin. The GaV–Gc transition marks the end of the co-evolution of the spectral total area and carbonate content, implying the influence of carbonate content in spectral features. This limit also marks a decrease of density of the sedimentary materials, increasing the reservoir quality of the GaV layers. The gas content C1 is variable but quite high. The decrease of the GR from the bottom to top of section as well as the increase of the carbonate content marks the change in the paleogeographic conditions. The end of the clastic environment due to fluvio-aeolian conditions is superimposed by the evidence of the marine event characterised by carbonate precipitations.

The third zone is in Middle Buntsandstein from 1960 to 2132 m records a fracture density of 0.56 fractures per meter. In this part of the Grès Vosgien, spectral total area values become more scattered, which is coherent with the higher fracture density compared to the second zone. Both GR and C1 values are very stable and very low. Indeed, here the mineralogy linked to fractures greatly influence the spectral feature producing changes of mineralogical content over a short distance.

The fourth zone is at the base on Lower Buntsandstein, at the unconformity GA-LGV from 2155 to 2200 m with a fracture density of 0.85 fractures per meter. This zone shows a slight decrease of spectral total area response and more than 100 gAPI for GR total. Moreover, there are 5% for K from Lower LGV to Lower GA, indicating a high clay content in GA associated with the most fractured zone. Calcite content and C1 are very low in this section. Despite the high fracture density, and the increase of K, the spectral total area is stable and does not reflect the presence of clay minerals in this zone.

These four zones characterized by varying fracture densities reveal also two distinct thermal gradient trends within the borehole. The first trend, extending from the top of the CC formation to the upper part of the UGV, exhibits a thermal gradient primarily controlled by the local major fractures. Also, the temperature log has been acquired in this section behind the casing of the well, suggesting that the temperature anomalies influence could even be higher on the temperature log if it has been measured in the open hole. The second trend, from the top of the UGV down to the GaA, is characterized by a continuous and slow increase of the temperature with depth with no major temperature anomaly suggesting a fluid contribution controlled by the matrix porosity and the small-scale fractures.

From a mineralogical point of view, the spectral total area in the Muschelkalk formation (from CC to Gc) is primarily influenced by the sedimentary mineral assemblages, particularly the distribution and evolution of carbonate content across the lithostratigraphic units. However, overlapped on this sedimentary control, localized spectral anomalies, such as those observed at the MB–CO transition, indicate the additional influence of fracture related mineralization, notably secondary clays and carbonates. However, the origin rather lithostratigraphic or fracture-related of the carbonates is difficult to decipher.

In contrast, within the Buntsandstein, the spectral total area shows limited correlation with the sedimentary mineralogy, such as the distribution of clay minerals. Instead, the spectral response appears to be primarily governed by the mineralogical signature of the fracture network, especially in intervals where fracture density is high. In these fractured zones, short-range variations

in mineral composition, linked to fracture fillings or hydrothermal alteration, dominate the spectral signal, overshadowing the underlying lithological framework.

After an analysis of the SWIR spectroscopy, the fracture densities and the thermal trends at a large wavelength through the Muschelkalk and the Buntsandstein formations, a more detailed focus has been zone at the scale of individual fractured zone in the GRT-1 well.

FZ1660: An important positive temperature anomaly (+2°C) is spatially correlated with mud losses, high porosity and low bulk densities. On the image logs, two major fractures are visible at 1660.94 and 1664.34 m. These correlations reflect the occurrence of a permeable fracture zone containing two major fractures channelizing brine between the Muschelkalk formation and the well. Gas venues are very stable and rather low. They are not disturbed by the presence of fractures. Spectral total area values are rather low in this zone. This zone contains high values of calcimetry which is due to the occurrence of carbonate minerals from the Muschelkalk formation but could also be due to the presence of secondary calcite precipitating in open fractures.

FZ1710: A very low thermal anomaly (+0.3°C) is visible on the thermal gradient, but no gas venue and no mud losses are correlated. The calcimetry and spectral total area values show sharp decreases suggesting an “open” zone. On the image logs, we can identify 3 fractures, but this zone does not seem to contribute efficiently to the flowrate of the well. Gas venues like methane and mud losses are rather stable and low. This zone could reflect the occurrence of a permeable zone but contributing very low to the flow.

Between the two important thermal anomalies visible in the Muschelkalk (FZ1660, FZ1760), the temperature log shows minor anomalies such as the one described in FZ1710. However, such features do not show any evidence of permeability as there is no tangible mud losses associated.

FZ1760: An important negative temperature anomaly (-2.5°C) is correlated with gas venue (30000 ppm of C1), important mud losses, with high porosity and low

density, and high values of GR (182 gAPI of total GR and 4% of K). On the image log, one major fracture at 1759.99 m could channelize brine from the Muschelkalk limestone to the well. The high GR content and K content could be related to the occurrence of clay minerals. Spectral total area response is also quite high. These anomalies are spatially correlated with a very low calcite content, which could reflect a zone that has been depleted because of intense hydrothermal circulations.

FZ1815: A small temperature anomaly (+0.3°C) also visible on the thermal gradient is correlated with gas venue (600 ppm) and a GR increase (646 gAPI). On the image log, several fractures and eventually one major fracture at 1814.27 m could channelize brine from the Grès à Voltzia to the well. GR, K and spectral total area contents are positively correlated as well as mud losses. These correlations reflect the occurrence of a permeable zone having a very low flow contribution.

FZ1995: This zone is located at the top of the MGV. A calcimetry peak, a SWIR peak, a porosity peak, and a very small gas venue are correlated to a very small bump on the temperature log visible on the thermal gradient. At this depth, a zone with fracture occurrences and eventually 3 major fractures that could channelize the flow, at 1989.46, 1995.06 and 2000.52 m is visible. This zone could be a permeable zone poorly contributing to the flow. After these measurements displayed in this study, this zone has been chemically stimulated (Vidal et al., 2016) by dissolving the carbonates filling the fractures from 1925 to 2050 m but with no major post-stimulation increase of permeability. Hence, the fracture at 1995.06 m contains also fillings of euhedral quartz and barite (Vidal et al., 2016).

FZ2200: A small temperature anomaly (+0.3°C) is visible on the thermal gradient and correlated to a cluster of fractures, but no major fracture is identifiable. This zone could be permeable because of the sedimentary interface between the GA and the GaV which is also the most fractured zone in both GRT-1 and GRT-2 wells (FZ2455) (Figure 2 and 3).

Figure 2: Composite log of the GRT-1 well, showing from left to right the well completion, the lithostratigraphy (CC: Couches à Cératites, CE: Calcaire à Entroques, DL: Dolomie à Lingules, MB: Marnes Bariolées, CO: Dolomies & Calcaires Ondulés & Couches à Myacites, GC: Grès Coquiller, GaV: Grès à Voltzia, CI : Couches Intermédiaires, U-M-LGV : Upper-Middle-Lower Grès Vosgien, GA : Grès d’Annweiler, GaA : Grès anté-Annweiler) according to (Durringer et al., 2019), porosity, density, gamma-ray, temperature, gas venue, mud losses, and fracture density and borehole image logs.

4.2 GRT-2 well

A first description at a large scale is proposed, before detailing each permeable fracture zone and their well logs responses. All the depths are expressed in measured depth (MD).

The production well GRT-2 is less documented than the injection well GRT-1, hence, during the drilling the Muschelkalk section was unstable and thus only the Buntsandstein was logged with static geophysical data (Figure 3).

Between the Upper Muschelkalk and the UGV units, spectral values present highly erratic behavior. The highest values are consistently associated with positive thermal anomalies and gas influxes, with this pattern observed at each lithological transition. No direct correlation is found between spectral values and carbonate content, indicating that this interval is dominated by mineralogical variations typically linked to fractured zones.

From the top of the UGV to the base of the GaA, spectral values remain relatively high but scattered, without any clear large-scale trend. This interval is also characterized by progressively increasing temperatures with depth, suggesting a thermal influence related to fracture density. Four zones can be described in this interval. The first identified zone, extending from the top to the base of the UGV (from 2130 to 2240 m), is defined by a fracture density of 0.43 fractures per meter. Spectral total area values in this interval are highly erratic, yet consistently so across the entire section. The second zone from 2246 to 2264 m is marked by a steep fracture density gradient (1.32 fractures per meter), large open fractures, and a well-defined positive temperature anomaly. The third zone, located between the top of the MG and the base of the LG (from 2266 to 2385 m), shows a lower fracture density (0.4 fractures per meter). Spectral values remain erratic, accompanied by elevated total GR values. In addition, resistivity values increase

significantly at the base of this zone, particularly at the interface between the MGV and the LGV.

Unfortunately, the quality of the image logs disabled to observe natural fractures from 2365 to 2450 m, but at the LGV–GaA unconformity, spectral values become slightly more stable.

The fourth zone from 2450 to 2475 m is characterized by a high fracture density of 0.62 fractures per meter. The transition from GA to GaA is characterized by a sharp increase in GR K, a significant drop in the thermal gradient, and the presence of open fractures. These observations suggest that the recorded temperature anomalies are controlled by a permeable fracture network in this interval.

Permeable zones in the Muschelkalk show the same trend than in the GRT-1 well: two major zones seem to be permeable behind the casing of the well, suggesting that the temperature anomalies influence could even be higher, and that the permeability is mostly controlled by fractures rather than matrix porosity in the Muschelkalk.

FZ1820: This temperature anomaly ($>+2^{\circ}\text{C}$) is located at the transition between the Keuper and the Couches à Cératites and correlated with high values of calcimetry and gas venues at 1833 m.

FZ1875: A temperature anomaly (-1°C) is correlated with high calcimetry values and gas venues at 1865 and 1880 m.

FZ2130: An important SWIR peak is present in this zone with values up to 67 a.u.. This is only correlated with a gas venue and an increase in calcimetry. No

significant temperature anomaly is visible on the temperature log and only a very small one is visible on the thermal gradient. The zone is fractured, and one major fracture could be identified at 2131.82 m which could contribute to the flow. As this zone is located just after the way out of the casing at the emplacement of a well section change, the increase in SWIR could also be due to re-drilling through cement.

FZ2190: A small temperature anomaly ($+0.4^{\circ}\text{C}$) also visible on the thermal gradient is present at 2190 m, correlated with an increase in porosity and in electrical resistivity, a gas venue is present one meter below and a major fracture is present at 2189.82 m.

FZ2260: An important thermal anomaly ($+1.6^{\circ}\text{C}$) is visible also on the thermal gradient around 2260 m. This is correlated with a peak in SWIR, an increase in porosity, a peak in GR total and in K, but no significant gas venue was recorded. This zone is located at the interface of the UGV and MGV and is highly fractured. Three major fractures have been identified at 2254.68, 2258.89 and 2259.68 m which could channelize the flow but the entire zone by its high fracture density (1.32 frac/m) could contribute to the permeability.

FZ2455: A small temperature anomaly (-0.5°C) is visible on the thermal gradient and correlated to a cluster of fractures with a quite high density (0.62 frac/m), and a major fracture is identifiable at 2454.70 m. The permeability of this zone could be due to the sedimentary interface between the GA and the GaA which is also the most fractured zone in GRT-1 well (FZ2200) (Figure 2 and 3).

Figure 3: Composite log of the GRT-2 well, showing from left to right the well completion, the lithostratigraphy (K: Keuper, CC: Couches à Céraités, CE: Calcaire à Entroques, DL: Dolomie à Lingules, MB: Marnes Bariolées, CO: Dolomies & Calcaires Ondulés & Couches à Myacites, GC: Grès Coquiller, GaV: Grès à Voltzia, CI: Couches Intermédiaires, U-M-LGV : Upper-Middle-Lower Grès Vosgien, GA : Grès d’Annweiler, GaA : Grès anté-Annweiler) according to (Durringer et al., 2019), porosity, density, gamma-ray, temperature, gas venue, mud losses, and fracture data.

5. DISCUSSION

The temperature log allows to detect main zones contributing to the flow between the formation and the well. We assume that these zones are governed by major fractures channelizing the flow such as at 1660 m and 2200 m in GRT-1 well, and at 1820, 1875, 2260 and 2455 m in the GRT-2 well. The other zones that display small thermal anomalies at 1710, 1815, 1995 and 2200 m in the GRT-1 well and at 2130 and 2190 m in the GRT-2 well could be either related to the contribution of small-scale fractures or even to the matrix porosity of the rock. These secondary flow incomes from the formation to the well could be important but may be smoothed because present on a larger depth section.

These observations do not enable to differentiate the intensity and importance of the contribution of fractures

or matrix in such a dual media affected by both fractures and matrix porosity.

In both wells, permeable fractures influence in the Muschelkalk is visible on the temperature log although the equilibrium temperature was measured as this section was already cemented and cased, suggesting a very strong flow.

In both wells, the presence of these localized and important temperature anomalies which seem to be linked to major individual fractures in the Muschelkalk, added to a quite low fracture density (0.44 frac/m) and a porosity measured on core samples is also lower in the Muschelkalk than in the Buntsandstein (Heap et al., 2019, 2017) as well as visible on the porosity and density logs (Figure 2 and 3). This suggests that the Muschelkalk limestone permeability is governed by major individual fractures rather than by the formation porosity.

In both wells, an increase of the temperature log is observable at the way out of the casing. This increase is not interpreted as a temperature anomaly induced by a natural fracture channelizing the flow but as the evidence that the entire formation of the Buntsandstein is contributing to the flow with the porous matrix or with a diffuse fracture network, on the entire section and not only in localized zones governed by clearly identified fractures, even if in the case of the GRT-2 well, major fractures that could channelize the flow are also identified in the Buntsandstein.

In both wells, a temperature anomaly is visible at the interface between the GaA and the GA. In GRT-1 this permeable zone has been linked to a zone with a high density of fractures, and in GRT-2 as well, however in the GRT-2 well, in addition to the small-scale fractures, a major fracture is visible on the image logs.

The spectral response in the GRT-1 well, located more distal from the Rittershoffen fault, is primarily controlled by mineralogical variations associated with hydrothermal alteration related to fractures. As fracture density increases with depth, localized changes in mineralogy and especially secondary clay minerals and carbonates, generate a scattered spectral total area profile. However, in intervals where fracture density becomes very high (e.g., in the fourth zone), the mineralogical signal from fracture fillings dominates the spectral response, leading to a smoother evolution of the SWIR total area with depth. In this context, the SWIR data not only reflect mineral assemblages but also act as a reliable indicator of major permeable fracture zones.

In contrast, the GRT-2 well, which is more proximal to the fault, exhibits a more uniform fracture density throughout the logged section. This results in a consistently scattered SWIR response with depth, without the pronounced transitions observed in GRT-1. The spectral signal in GRT-2 appears less sensitive to discrete mineralogical shifts and more reflective of a continuous fracture-controlled alteration system. Overall, the comparison suggests that while SWIR data can identify fracture-controlled mineralization in both wells, its stratigraphic expression varies with structural position relative to the fault and the spatial distribution of fracture density.

Surprisingly, the fracture density is increasing with depth in the GRT-1 well but not in the GRT-2 well, according to the SWIR data correlating the proximity of the fault, one might expect an increase of the fracture density with depth (and the proximity of the granite) rather in the GRT-2 well than in the GRT-1 well. One hypothesis could be that the SWIR increase with depth and the proximity of the Rittershoffen fault intersecting the granite in the GRT-2 well could rather be due to hydrothermal alteration than to the fracture density. This suggests that hydrothermal alteration propagation can be controlled also by a porous media and not only by a fractured media.

6. CONCLUSION

The correlation between static geophysical logs, dynamic well logs and data acquired on the rock cuttings allow to evidence the fracture-controlled permeability of the Muschelkalk and its low matrix permeability in contrast with the porous-controlled permeability of the Buntsandstein which can be locally enhanced by the presence of fractures.

The SWIR spectroscopy appears to be a useful tool for mineralogical estimates and quantification in sedimentary formations and further studies led in the framework of the PhD of Manaarii Salmon will surely allow to decipher the contribution of carbonates and clay minerals in the spectral response.

REFERENCES

- Baillieux, P., Schill, E., Edel, J., Mauri, G., 2013. Localization of temperature anomalies in the Upper Rhine Graben: insights from geophysics and neotectonic activity. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00206814.2013.794914>
- Baujard, C., Genter, A., Dalmais, E., Maurer, V., Hehn, R., Rosillette, R., Vidal, J., Schmittbuhl, J., 2017. Hydrothermal characterization of wells GRT-1 and GRT-2 in Rittershoffen, France: Implications on the understanding of natural flow systems in the Rhine graben. *Geothermics* 65, 255–268. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geothermics.2016.11.001>
- Duringer, P., Aichholzer, C., Orciani, S., Genter, A., 2019. The complete lithostratigraphic section of the geothermal wells in Rittershoffen (Upper Rhine Graben, eastern France): a key for future geothermal wells. *BSGF - Earth Sci. Bull.* 190, 13. <https://doi.org/10.1051/bsgf/2019012>
- Evans, K.F., Genter, A., Sausse, J., 2005. Permeability creation and damage due to massive fluid injections into granite at 3.5 km at Soultz: 1. Borehole observations. *J. Geophys. Res. Solid Earth* 110. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004JB003168>
- Genter, A., Evans, K., Cuenot, N., Fritsch, D., Sanjuan, B., 2010. Contribution of the exploration of deep crystalline fractured reservoir of Soultz to the knowledge of enhanced geothermal systems (EGS). *Comptes Rendus Geosci., Vers l'exploitation des ressources géothermiques profondes des systèmes hydrothermaux convectifs en milieux naturellement fracturés* 342, 502–516. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crte.2010.01.006>
- Glaas, C., Vidal, J., Patrier, P., Girard, J.-F., Beaufort, D., Petit, S., Genter, A., 2019. How do secondary minerals in granite help distinguish paleo- from present-day permeable fracture zones? Joint interpretation of SWIR spectroscopy and geophysical logs in the geothermal wells of Northern Alsace.

- Geofluids 2019, 1–20.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/8231816>
- Heap, M.J., Kushnir, A.R.L., Gilg, H.A., Violay, M.E.S., Harlé, P., Baud, P., 2019. Petrophysical properties of the Muschelkalk from the Soultz-sous-Forêts geothermal site (France), an important lithostratigraphic unit for geothermal exploitation in the Upper Rhine Graben. *Geotherm. Energy* 7, 27. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40517-019-0145-4>
- Heap, M.J., Kushnir, A.R.L., Gilg, H.A., Wadsworth, F.B., Reuschlé, T., Baud, P., 2017. Microstructural and petrophysical properties of the Permo-Triassic sandstones (Buntsandstein) from the Soultz-sous-Forêts geothermal site (France). *Geotherm. Energy Heidelb.* 5, 1–37. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40517-017-0085-9>
- Pribnow, D., Schellschmidt, R., 2000. Thermal tracking of upper crustal fluid flow in the Rhine graben. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 27, 1957–1960. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2000GL008494>
- Schlumberger, 2018. HRLA High-Resolution Laterolog Array | Schlumberger [WWW Document]. URL https://www.slb.com/services/characterization/petrophysics/wireline/legacy_services/high_res_array.aspx (accessed 12.3.18).
- Serra, O., Serra, L., 2000. *Diagraphies, Acquisition et applications*, Serralog. ed.
- Vidal, J., Genter, A., Chopin, F., 2017. Permeable fracture zones in the hard rocks of the geothermal reservoir at Rittershoffen, France. *J. Geophys. Res. Solid Earth* 122, 4864–4887.
- Vidal, J., Genter, A., Schmittbuhl, J., 2016. Pre- and post-stimulation characterization of geothermal well GRT-1, Rittershoffen, France: insights from acoustic image logs of hard fractured rock. *Geophys. J. Int.* 206, 845–860. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gji/ggw181>

Acknowledgements

This project research, FindHeat was funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101147171. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The authors are grateful to ECOGI for the Rittershoffen dataset and to the PEPR Fossé rhéna.